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Comparing Flowchart and Swim Lane Activity Diagram for Aiding Transitioning to Object-Oriented Implementation

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ABSTRACT

Object Oriented Programming (OOP) paradigm is one of the programming styles that emerged in response to the challenge of designing complex software. However, students find it hard to conceptualize objects when they were already accustomed to non Object Oriented approach to programming. This paper hypothesizes that introducing Object Oriented (OO) notations to students during the design phase will smoothen their transition to Object Oriented Programming. To test the hypothesis, an experiment was conducted with the students of Al-Qalam University Katsina, Nigeria. The participating students were divided into two groups: (i) *Flowchart group* - representing the classical approach where flowcharts were used to design solutions. (ii) *Activity Diagram group* - which represents the control group in which swim lane activity diagram, as Object Oriented notation, was introduced to them at the design phase. Both groups were later introduced to Class Responsibility Collaborators (CRC) cards as an Object Oriented implementation model. The students were tested, four different times, on how well they converted flowcharts or activity diagrams, as the case may be, into Class Responsibility Collaborators cards, and their performances were recorded. The results were analyzed using Repeated Measure Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Unexpectedly, the *Flowchart group* outperformed the *Activity Diagram group* but the results were not statistically significant. Similarly, there was no statistical difference between males' and females' performances.

INTRODUCTION

Computer programming is an important skill across diverse fields and disciplines and even more so for Computing Science students. As computers are becoming more pervasive, the skill is one of the necessary requirements for continuous automation of the modern world as well as for the maintenance of the already automated systems. For computing based disciplines such as Computer Science and Software Engineering, programming courses are taught at many levels - from the year of entry to the year of graduation. Despite the criticality of programming, acquiring the skills remains a challenge for many students (Mehmood *et al.*, 2020).

Although there are many reasons why students struggle with programming (Oroma *et al.*, 2012; Qian *et al.*, 2017; Sheard *et al.*, 2009) the following are the most relevant to this paper:

- i. The cognitive intensity that is required to learn the low-level details of programming.
- ii. Pedagogically, students have been literary dragged to it (the programming).

For the low level details inhibiting the comprehension of programming as outlined in (i) above, over the years programming languages have evolved in which the level of abstraction has been raised. In the process of abstraction evolution, many programming styles/paradigms emerged. One of the emerged paradigms is the Object Oriented Programming (OOP) paradigm developed out of the desire to manage complexity and improve productivity in software development. It is a programming style that uses real world "objects" to design computer programs. OOP reduces the conceptual gap from the design space to

the implementation space (Bucci *et al.*, 2002; Evans, 2004) because the program is conceptualized as a collection of objects interacting to achieve a common goal (Hourani *et al.*, 2019). Similarly, programs developed using OOP are easier to maintain because objects are easier to trace and update (G. Antonioli *et al.*, 2001; Giulio Antonioli *et al.*, 2000; Bianchi *et al.*, 2000). Further, OOP provides additional support for code reuse through inheritance and additional support for flexibility through polymorphism (Daly *et al.*, 1996).

With OOP, professional software developers enjoy plethora of supports. For example, in testing, there exist unit testing frameworks (Daka & Fraser, 2014); in mapping objects to records in a relational database, there exist Object Relational Mapping frameworks (Torres *et al.*, 2017); in design, there exists a collection of design patterns to solve similar recurring problems (Gamma *et al.*, 1995); in source code organization, there exists guidelines and tool support for refactoring (Daughtry III & Kannampallil, 2005; Martin, 2018).

As the saying goes that a picture may be worth more than a thousand words, it was envisaged that diagramming will improve comprehension of computer programming (Smetsers-Weeda & Smetsers, 2017) as pictorial representation simultaneously raises the level of abstraction from low to high and can be used to improve over teaching pedagogy. Consequently, diagrams were also introduced to represent the design of a solution that will be implemented as a computer program. One of the diagrams used for the design is Flowchart. Similarly, one of the diagrams used for OO design is Activity Diagram and some of the notations used in documenting OO

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implementation are Class Responsibility Collaborators (CRC) models. We provide the details of the flowchart, the activity diagram, and the CRC in the *Methodology section*.

Statement of the problem

In the introductory computing courses, students are expected to learn how to design solutions to computing problems using notations such as flowcharts and then subsequently learn how to translate the flowchart into an algorithm to be implemented using the procedural style of programming. Later, and in subsequent courses, students are introduced to the OOP programming style as another implementation alternative. However, since students were already accustomed to procedural implementation and knew that the approach ‘works,’ they struggled to conceive objects when introduced later as a viable alternative (Börstler *et al.*, 2008; Cutts *et al.*, 2019; Kölling, 1999). Students already learned how to design solutions to problems without the concept of objects in the scheme of things and were later required to transition to Object Oriented implementation. One of the reasons for the struggle might be that they do not have a clue about objects in the design space but have been asked to reflect them in the implementation space, which requires unlearning the procedural style of implementation.

Thus, this paper aims to compare the effect of learning flowcharts, as non OO design notation, and activity diagram (an OO based design notation) in transitioning to Object Oriented implementation.

Research hypotheses

Given the above, we envisage that the students may find the transition easier if OO-notations were also introduced to them while learning diagrammatic designs of solutions to computing problems (see Figure 1). As such, the paper hypothesized the following:

- **H1:** Introducing activity diagrams to students at the design stage will improve their ease of transition to Object Oriented implementation.

- **H2:** there is a difference between males and females in transitioning to Object Oriented design (OOD).

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2.0 presents the research works related to this paper. Section 3.0 explains the methodology adopted in this paper and begins with the clarification of the research constructs and ends with the detailed settings and execution of the study. Section 4.0 discusses the results obtained and highlights what could be threats to the validity of the research. Lastly, Section 5.0 concludes the paper.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Existing studies mostly focus on the performance of students in programming, generally, and not specifically on OOP. For instance, Olalekan *et al.*, (Akinola & Nosiru, 2014) investigated the effect of students’ attitudes on ease of learning programming. They used students’ attitudes such as regular attendance to lectures and interest in programming as some of the research

constructs. They found that regular attendance at lectures was the most important factor, followed by the students’ interest in programming. Other factors that were found to affect students’ performance in learning programming were positive perception about the programming and the lecturers’ attitudes toward the students. Similarly, Amnouyochokanant *et al.*, (Amnouyochokanant *et al.*, 2021) assessed the effect of students’ attitudes toward programming and its learning performance but with different sets of research constructs. Some of the research constructs used and found to be significant predictors of high-performance in programming were positive self-efficacy and creativity.

There has been a continuous search for effective techniques to teach OOP. For instance, Loksa *et al.*, (Loksa *et al.*, 2016) proposed an approach aimed at teaching student problem solving skills. The approach put emphasis in creating an explicit mental model of the problem to be solved and depicting the coding as a mere translation of the mental model. Other techniques introduced include visualizing the progress in creating the solution as well as explicit support for promptings to reflect on their strategies to solve the problem. Similarly, (Bucci *et al.*, 2002) reported how they worked in transitioning from the traditional imperative model to an Object Oriented model of learning programming for over ten years and concluded that teaching Object Oriented programming is not as simple or “natural” but difficult to convey to the students the advantages and methodologies associated with Object Oriented programming.

Still on the search for effective pedagogies to teach OOP, (Anfurrutia *et al.*, 2017) Implemented Kolb’s learning theory in visual programming environments in order to help students to become competent in Object Oriented programming. The authors analyzed the acceptance by the students as well as its effect on their motivation. Kolb’s learning theory entails four cycles that learners must undergo to acquire knowledge. The cycles are: (i) carrying out a specific activity to have concrete experience (ii) reflecting on the experience from the carried out activity, (iii) conceptualizing the theoretical aspects of the activity, and (iv) applying the knowledge acquired in new scenarios or situations. The visual environments used were BlueJ and Greenfoot – another IDE for learning and teaching based on simulations or games. For the acceptance, students indicated that they would prefer using the tools even though females’ responses were more negative than males’. As for motivation, the results were not as good as the authors’ expected. However, the approach does not consider the problem analysis space.

In another study on the pedagogical approach to teaching OOP, (Uysal, 2012) explored the effects of ‘objects-first’ and ‘objects-late’ methods of teaching Object Oriented Programming (OOP). The author experimented with two groups of students. The scope of the course was identical for the two groups but the structure of the contents differed in sequence. Both the participants in the two groups used BlueJ IDE to eliminate the possible

effects of different instructional tools. The objects first learners used all visual functionalities of BlueJ IDE while the objects late learners started with only the text-based interfaces of BlueJ and were instructed to use the visual support only in the last lectures. The study found that the learners instructed with the objects-first method achieved higher learning outcomes.

In a similar context of smooth transitioning from process engineering to process control engineering, (Vogel-Heuser *et al.*, 2003) explored the benefit of modeling. From the experiment they had conducted with students, it turned out that the groups that previously modeled the process had advantages in describing the several process steps and structuring the Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) program.

In another exploratory study, (Ivanović *et al.*, 2015) investigated different aspects of teaching introductory courses on Object Oriented Programming at three (3) universities in different European countries. They

compared different aspects and experiences from Object Oriented programming courses that were taught in the three (3) institutions. They found that all the institutions use various forms of course delivery. This indicates that a generic strategy for teaching transition to OOP has not been found yet. However, in all three (3) institutions, technology-enhanced learning tools (TEL) played a central role in the OOP courses offered. In particular, BlueJ - an integrated development environment (IDE) for learning OOP with Java language designed for educational purposes- was found to be used in all three institutions.

METHODOLOGY

Figure 1 represents the conceptual model of this paper. In the Figure, flowcharting represents the art of non Object Oriented problem solving using flowcharts while Activity diagraming represents the art of Object Oriented problem solving using activity diagrams. Ease

Figure 1: Conceptual model

of transition to Object Oriented programming is assessed based on how well the class responsibility collaborators (CRC) model is produced. We expect gender to play a moderating role.

To make the discussion in this section more concrete, we introduce a trivial problem of manual booking of an appointment with a dentist. In the manual process, a patient calls the dental clinic. The receptionist receives the call and guides the patients on the available slots. The patient selects one of the available slots, which the receptionist will reserve and informs the patient of the appointed schedule. For brevity, we assume that the patient has already registered with the clinic. In this section, we will discuss the background concepts with the solutions to the stated problem using a flowchart, an activity diagram, and class responsibility collaborators (CRC) cards.

Flowchart

A flowchart is a diagrammatic representation of steps to solving a given problem. Although it can also be used for other things such as the analysis of the problem or documentation of a process, we use a flowchart in

this paper in the context of representing a solution to a computing problem. A flowchart is an approximate representation of an algorithm to solve a specific computing problem.

A flowchart can be used to teach problem solving without getting deep into the low-level details of complete syntaxes of a programming language so that learning can be focused on the problem solving aspect. Flowchart-based programming environments are also used to entice students to programming with the big picture of the intended solution in their minds(Chen & Morris, 2005; Smetsers-Weeda & Smetsers, 2017).

The flowchart in Figure 2 represents the design of an automated system to solve the problem of manually booking of an appointment with a dentist as outlined above. As shown in the figure, after starting the system, it displays the list of available slots for patients to request an appointment with a dentist. The patient would then select a slot and request its booking. The system then checks to confirm if the slot has not been reserved for other patients since, due to time lag, another patient might have requested and booked the selected slot. If the slot has already been taken, the system returns the patient to the

list of available slots otherwise the system will reserve the slot and send a notification email to the patient. Lastly, the booking information shall be displayed to the patient.

Activity Diagram

The activity diagram is one of the behavioural diagrams of Unified Modelling Language (UML).

Figure 2: Flowchart illustration of a dentist booking system

It is similar to the flowchart as it can be used to diagrammatically represent a series of actions or flow of control to solve a given problem. Similarly, it can be used for other things such as modelling business processes or behavioural descriptions of a use case diagram (Jeyaraj & Sauter, 2014; Khaled Abdelazim *et al.*, 2020).

Swim lane activity is an activity diagram that is used to show which system actor is responsible for what, in addition to the representation of the series of actions or flow of control to solve the problem. Thus, the presence of objects as well as their high level responsibilities can be captured explicitly as system actors on the diagram. Swim lane activity diagrams are also powerful models

in model-driven engineering (MDA) in the sense that they could also be transformed into other models or executable (Zhang *et al.*, 2012). The diagram may as well be recovered from Object Oriented source codes through reverse engineering (Martinez *et al.*, 2011).

Figure 3 is an activity diagram that represents the same solution depicted in Figure 2 as Flowchart. It is a swim lane activity diagram because the responsibilities are indicated under the System and Patient as the main actors.

Class Responsibility Collaboration (CRC)

Class Responsibilities Collaborators (CRC) was invented by Ward Cunningham and Kent Beck (Beck & Cunningham,

Figure 3: Swim lane activity diagram representing the design of a dentist booking system

1989; Cunningham & Beck, 1986) as an approach to discovering and documenting objects in OO design. CRC was initially designed to simplify learning OOP but has also been used in professional software development such as Agile's eXtreme Programming (XP) (Beck, 1999).

A class represents a template from which similar objects are created, responsibility is something that a class knows or does, and a collaborator is another class that a class interacts with to fulfill its responsibilities. CRC card is a 3x5 index card and is partitioned into three: the first

scores of computing courses ($t(25)=14.61$, $p=0.000$; $t(25)=15.22$, $p=0.000$; $t(25)=17.87$, $p=0.000$; $t(25)=13.86$, $p=0.000$).

In the first, second, and fourth tests, the means for the males were 85.61, 80.83, and 83.06 respectively. The means for females were 81.63, 74.38, and 80.63 respectively. Thus, the means for the male were higher. In contrast, in the third test, the means for females were slightly higher which was 83.13 against males' 82.22. However, there was no significant interaction between gender and the performance $F(1,3) = 0.531$, $p=0.663$.

In the first, second, and third tests, the mean for the *Flowchart group* were 86.0, 84.55, and 85.46 respectively, while for the *Activity Diagram group* the means were 83.2, 74.67, and 80.33 respectively. Thus, the means for the *Flowchart group* were higher than the expected outcome. In the fourth test, the means were comparably very close: for the *Flowchart Group* 82.27 while for the *Activity Diagram group* 82.33.

In addition to the quantitative results analyzed above, the second author also profiled students' mistakes. In the *Flowchart group*, students found it difficult to distinguish between input/output and process symbol as both were used interchangeably. They were also not bothered to put the stop symbols at the end of the flowchart. Lastly, they use directional arrows inappropriately. For the *Activity Diagram group*, Students struggle with specifying the different actors in the different columns of the diagram. They mistook the end node and the end node. Lastly, they often place a process in a column it does not belong to. Nonetheless, the students in both groups were making similar mistakes in the CRC such as skipping some of the responsibilities, interchanging the position of the responsibilities and collaborators, and not writing the class name.

DISCUSSION

It might be observed that the average score of the participants students was remarkably high considering the rate of failure in computer programming and problem solving related course (Omeh & Olelewe, 2021); It might be the case that only high-performing students volunteered to participate in the study. Similar to the studies in (Amnouyochokanant *et al.*, 2021; Omeh & Olelewe, 2021), no significant interaction between gender and the performance. Thus, we reject the hypothesis that there is a difference between males and females in transitioning to Object Oriented design (OOD). The findings contrast with the results obtained in (Anfurrutia *et al.*, 2017) where males' and females' preferences differed significantly. Similar to the results obtained in (Vilner *et al.*, 2007), there was no significant interaction between the different groups and the performance ($F(1, 3) = 1.160$, $p=0.331$). Consequently, we reject the hypothesis that introducing activity diagrams to students at the design stage will improve their ease of transition to Object Oriented implementation. It likely that the sample used in the study was not large enough. Thus, further study should

be conducted with large and (semi)randomised samples.

Threat to Validity

It may be argued that the activity diagram may not be the right notation to test the ease of transitioning from procedural style as previous studies mostly used Integrated Development Environments (IDEs) (Anfurrutia *et al.*, 2017; Ivanović *et al.*, 2015; Uysal, 2012). However, using IDEs assumed that students already know how to design solutions before their implementation using a specific programming environment. Our study focused on problem-solving without the cumbersome aspect of learning syntaxes of any programming language. In addition, modeling using, diagrammatic notation, helps in bringing out the big picture of the intended solution (Vogel-Heuser *et al.*, 2003).

There was a chance of sampling error as the students' average scores were significantly high. Nevertheless, since the individual scores ranged from 50 to 100 and there was a total of 96 data points, any variations between the groups that were not down to chance should have been detected. However, further study with large and (semi) randomised samples may give better insight. Similarly, the results may not be generalizable as the participated students were mainly novices. Nonetheless, different backgrounds do not necessarily matter (Vilner *et al.*, 2007).

CONCLUSION

When learners were already accustomed to the procedural implementation style, they may struggle to conceive objects in object oriented programming despite the advantage of the Object Oriented style over the procedural style. This paper conceived that introducing Object Oriented modeling at the solution design phase may help ease the transition to Object Oriented programming. Thus, the paper experimented to test the effect of object oriented modeling in easing the transition to Object Oriented style. The results show that introducing the Object Oriented modeling will not achieve that desired effect as expected. The paper suggests further studies with large and randomise sample.

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